

EFFECTS OF METABOLIC SYNDROME ON UROLOGICAL DISEASES.

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Abstract. This article provides information on the impact of Metabolic syndrome on urological diseases.

Key words: metabolic syndrome, urolithiasis, body mass index, hypercalciuria, hyperphosphaturia, hypomagnuria, hyperoxaluria and hyperinsulinemia, urinary stone.

ВЛИЯНИЕ МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКОГО СИНДРОМА НА УРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ
ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о влиянии Метаболического синдрома на урологические заболевания.

Ключевые слова: метаболический синдром, мочекаменная болезнь, индекс массы тела, гиперкальциурия, гиперфосфатурия, гипомagniурия, гипероксалурия и гиперинсулинемия, мочевиые камни.

The growing statistics of urological diseases in our region is a serious concern. In Uzbekistan, more than 5 thousand out of 100 thousand residents suffer from diseases of the body system organs every year. This is due not only to the environmental situation in some cities of the Republic, but also to the way of life of the population, improper nutrition and other factors that negatively affect human health. Most often, the indicator of pain with the disease is observed in the Navoi region. It is followed by Khorezm, Samarkand and Jizzakh regions. Uzbekistan today is one of the leaders in the problem of urinary bladder disease, the urolithiasis recurrence in the country is more than 45 percent.

In parallel with the increase in metabolic syndrome, the increase in urolithiasis (from 20 to 40% in the population), the prevalence of which has a pandemic scale, is of concern. Currently, sufficient evidence has been collected to show that urolithiasis is a systemic disease with different forms of interaction with metabolic syndrome. A number of authors propose to consider urolithiasis as a renal manifestation of metabolic syndrome, the frequency of its detection reaches

50% in the presence of all components of metabolic syndrome. The synergistic effect of a number of metabolic syndrome components leads not only to the appearance of urinary stones, but also to an increased risk of recurrence after surgical removal, and the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying them are extremely complex and contradictory. Independent studies provide strong evidence that increases the risk of developing urolithiasis in people with obesity and metabolic syndrome.

The purpose of the study. Determination of the possible relationship of the development of urolithiasis in overweight and obese metabolically healthy patients by body mass index, urine pH and mineral composition categories of urolites.

Research results: our scientific studies have shown these results in patients with kidney-stone disease.

No	Surname, name	Age	Height	Weight	Body mass index (kg/m ²) norm (18.5 - 24.99)	Ratio between weight and length	Urine Ph	Stone type
1	Zuhriddinov L	32	172	80	27.04	body weight excess	5,45	oxalate stone
2	Yaxyayev U	25	173	79	26.4	body weight excess	6,35	oxalate stone
3	Mirzayev A	20	165	83	30.49	first degree obesity	5,75	oxalate stone
4	Turiboyeva A	52	167	78	27.94	body weight excess	6,4	oxalate stone
5	Shomaxmudova M	31	165	90	33.06	first degree obesity	6,11	oxalate stone
6	Xujakeshov A	43	178	93	29.35	body weight excess	6,12	oxalate stone
7	Safarova M	62	165	69	25.34	body weight excess	6,6	cystine stone
8	Bahodirov A	33	168	78	27.64	body weight excess	6.4	oxalate stone

In our studies, we calculated the body mass index indicator using the formula discovered by Adolf Ketley.

Body mass index = body weight (kg / height m²)

Body mass index	Body mass index ratio between weight and length of a person
16 and less	Significant deficiency of body weight
16—18,5	Lack of body weight
18,5—24,99	Norm
25—30	Excess body weight
30—35	first degree obesity
35—40	secondary obesity
40 and above	third degree obesity

In order to carry out the task aimed at determining the type of rock formation, a study of the mineral composition and structural properties of urinary stones was carried out using the X-ray phase analysis method (spectrometry method), which makes it possible to study the crystal structure of a small amount of substance in a mixture with other elements.

Conclusion. An increase in the body mass index is associated with a decrease in the acidity of the urine and the development of oxalate and phosphate-oxalate urolites. Prevention and treatment of obesity is a large medical and socio-economic task, the solution of which is not always successful. Various independent studies have shown that urolithiasis and obesity have common biochemical mechanisms that can reduce the risk of urinary stones. Lithogenic metabolic disorders, including increased body mass index, decreased urine volume, hypercalciuria, hyperphosphaturia, hypomagniuria, hyperoxaluria, and hyperinsulinemia, are the most important factors associated with obesity and the formation of urinary stones.

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